

Farm machinery

Manual rice transplanter use in Burma

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More than 3.5 million ha of the 4.8 million ha rice in Burma is transplanted. Transplanting traditionally is women's responsibility. The Agricultural Mechanization Department (AMD) and Agricultural Corporation (AC) reproduced 30 IRRI developed manually operated mechanical transplanters for field testing in 1979.

AMD made 10 modifications: replaced the operating handle with a better grip, changed to a free-hanging counter weight cam for better retraction of pickers, replaced the ratchet with an over-running clutch and the chain roller with a star wheel for better movement, changed the buckle for planting depth to a hook with screw and nut for easier fabrication, added a reinforcing bar and a coil spring between frame members for durability, inserted an inverted U-shaped holder in the pickers to improve hold, added an adjusting screw at the stop block to adjust picking angle, added a seedling guard plate to prevent the seed mat from deforming, put in a reinforcement bracket for each pivot pin for durability, and eliminated the flat carriage bar for better movement of the tray. Bamboo is used instead of wood in seedbed preparation to reduce costs.

The modified transplanter reduces transplanting costs 40%. Hand transplanting costs US\$26.79, the manual transplanter US\$17.66. (These estimates depend on the wage rate of an area, the cost of the transplanter, and its transplanting capacity. Soil type, level of land preparation, water depth, and operator skill also alter estimates.)

The government introduced the manual rice transplanter with dynamic demonstrations, but farmer adoption has been low (see table). Five problems merit consideration:

1. The rice area has not increased

Yearly manufacture and uses of manually operated mechanical transplanter in Burma.

Year	Manufacturer ^a	Number produced	Number in fields	Transplanted area (ha)
1980	AMD	300		
1981	AMD	1000		
1982	AMD	1000	750	4608
1983	HIC	1000	1000	4219
1984	HIC	500	697	1624
1985	HIC	100	1400	8097

^a HIC = Heavy Industries Corporation.

2. A well-organized program to train farmers to operate the transplanter is important.
3. Existing institutions and infrastructure need to be improved to provide repair and replacement facilities within easy reach of

farmers.

4. Target areas for adoption should have the right soil type, proper drainage capabilities, sufficient institutional and infrastructure support, and enough motivated farmers.
5. A well-organized research and development program is needed to solve specific problems in specific areas. □

Farming systems

Pigeonpea genotypes and rice yield in an intercropping system

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We tested different pigeonpea genotypes in an intercropping system with rice

during the 1986-87 wet season. Soil was laterite and sandy loam with pH 5.2, 0.37% total N, 16 kg available P/ha, and 160 kg available K/ha.

Nine pigeonpea genotypes were grown in paired rows of 30/90 cm alone and intercropped with Subhadra rice (90 d duration). Five rows of rice were planted in the interspace of pigeonpea. The intercrops received 30-18-25 kg NPK/ha, rice alone 60-18-25 kg NPK/ha, and pigeonpea alone 20-18-17 kg NPK/ha.

Pigeonpea genotypes differed in their effect on rice yield (see table). The

Yields of pigeonpea genotypes intercropped with rice. Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, 1986-87 wet season.

Genotype	Intercropped rice yield (t/ha)	Pigeonpea yield (t/ha)		Land equivalent ratio
		Alone	Intercropped	
Pigeonpea				
ICPL 138	1.7	0.6	0.2	1.16
ICPL 227	1.2	0.8	0.7	1.37
ICPL 265	1.2	0.6	0.5	1.40
ICPL 270	1.2	0.5	0.3	1.09
ICPL 295	1.3	0.4	0.4	1.56
ICPL 186	1.0	0.5	0.2	0.81
DAS83-1	1.1	0.8	0.3	0.88
DAS83-2	1.2	0.9	0.4	1.03
R60	1.1	1.2	0.9	1.24
Rice alone				
Subhadra	2.2			
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.21